

STRATEGIES FOR ENSURING PRAGMATIC ADEQUACY IN LITERARY TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *This article analyzes strategies for ensuring pragmatic adequacy in literary translation based on linguopragmatic and linguoculturological approaches. It substantiates the necessity of preserving not only semantic equivalence but also the communicative purpose, emotional impact, and cultural connotations of the text in the translation process. The study examines the main strategies for achieving pragmatic adequacy—adaptation, compensation, explicitation, and transformation—illustrated with examples.*

Keywords: *pragmatic adequacy, literary translation, equivalence, pragmatic adaptation, communicative impact, linguopragmatics, translation strategies, cultural reference*

Annotatsiya. *Mazkur maqolada badiiy tarjimada pragmatik moslikni ta’minlash strategiyalari lingvopragmatik va lingvokulturologik yondashuvlar asosida tahlil qilinadi. Tarjima jarayonida nafaqat semantik ekvivalentlik, balki matning kommunikativ maqsadi, emotsional ta’siri va madaniy konnotatsiyalarini saqlab qolish zarurligi asoslab beriladi. Tadqiqotda pragmatik moslikka erishishning asosiy strategiyalari – adaptatsiya, kompensatsiya, izohlash va transformatsiya usullari misollar asosida yoritiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *pragmatik moslik, badiiy tarjima, ekvivalentlik, pragmatik adaptatsiya, kommunikativ ta’sir, lingvopragmatika, tarjima strategiyalari, madaniy referentsiya*

Аннотация. *В данной статье анализируются стратегии обеспечения прагматической адекватности в художественном переводе на основе лингвопрагматического и лингвокультурологического подходов. Обосновывается необходимость сохранения в процессе перевода не только семантической эквивалентности, но и коммуникативной цели, эмоционального воздействия и культурных коннотаций текста. В исследовании рассматриваются основные стратегии достижения прагматической адекватности — адаптация, компенсация, экспликация и трансформация, проиллюстрированные примерами.*

Ключевые слова: *прагматическая адекватность, художественный перевод, эквивалентность, прагматическая адаптация, коммуникативное воздействие, лингвопрагматика, переводческие стратегии, культурная референция*

Introduction: In modern translation studies, the process of translating literary texts is regarded as a multilayered and complex phenomenon. Translation is not merely the transfer of linguistic units, but also the transmission of the pragmatic content of the text, namely the author’s communicative intent, emotional impact, and cultural context. The concept of pragmatic adequacy is one of the important categories in translation, as it implies preserving the functional and communicative aspects of the source text in translation. In literary texts in particular, accurately conveying imagery, stylistic devices, and cultural references is considered a primary task in ensuring pragmatic adequacy.

Literature Review: The problem of pragmatic adequacy and equivalence has been widely studied as one of the key theoretical directions in translation studies. This issue involves not only the formal correspondence of linguistic units in translation but also the preservation of the communicative purpose and pragmatic effect of the text. Paronyan analyzes the concepts of pragmatic adequacy and equivalence, emphasizing the importance of preserving communicative intent in translation [1]. This approach is based on interpreting translation not as a simple substitution of language, but as a complex communicative process. Shokhsanam and co-authors examine strategies for achieving pragmatic equivalence and demonstrate the effectiveness of adaptation and compensation methods [2]. Through adaptation, the text is culturally adjusted, while compensation restores lost pragmatic meanings using other means. These strategies serve to maintain pragmatic balance in the translation process.

Beibitova and co-authors analyze the impact of pragmatic factors on translation quality based on pragmlinguistic experience in literary translation [3]. The study reveals that pragmatic categories such as speech situation, addressee factor, and communicative intent directly influence the adequacy of translation results. Therefore, the pragmlinguistic approach is of significant theoretical and practical importance for translators. Bekmurodova and others examine the issue of ensuring pragmatic adequacy in translating cultural references and highlight the importance of intercultural differences [4]. Cultural elements are often context-dependent, and finding direct equivalents for them is difficult. Therefore, the translator must choose appropriate pragmatic solutions taking cultural context into account.

Djumabaeva and Jumamuratova analyze pragmatic potential and adaptation issues in literary translation, substantiating the importance of the translator's cultural competence [5]. According to them, the translator, as a mediator between two languages and cultures, must possess not only linguistic knowledge but also the ability to understand cultural differences. This enhances the pragmatic and communicative effectiveness of translation. Muradillayeva analyzes the theory of equivalence and its application in literary translation [6]. Equivalence manifests at different levels—semantic, syntactic, and pragmatic—and serves as an important criterion in the translation process. Based on this, the translator recreates the source text in the target language while preserving its content and function. Ilkhomidinova and Khodjalepesova analyze pragmatic and psycholinguistic transformations, emphasizing the importance of reader reception in literary translation [7]. Taking into account the cognitive characteristics, perception level, and cultural preparedness of the reader ensures effective understanding of the text. Thus, the pragmatic approach serves not only to convey meaning but also to optimize its reception in translation.

Research Methodology: This study employs comparative, pragmatic, linguoculturological, discursive, and contextual analysis methods in a comprehensive manner. These methods enabled a multifaceted examination of English and Uzbek literary texts and their translations. The comparative method was used to compare the source and target texts, identifying their structural, semantic, and stylistic features. This method was essential in analyzing transformations occurring in translation, equivalence levels, and translation strategies. Pragmatic analysis was used to identify the communicative purpose of the text, the author's intent, and its impact on the addressee. This approach helped reveal the functional load of textual units in speech situations and their implicit meanings. The linguoculturological approach made it possible to study cultural references, national values, and cultural codes reflected in the texts. This played an important role in identifying cultural differences between the two languages and their representation in translation.

Discursive analysis focused on the overall functional features of the text, the interrelation between its components, and communicative coherence. This method allowed the identification of the roles of textual units within discourse. Contextual analysis examined the role of linguistic units in speech environments, their context-dependent semantic changes, and pragmatic load. Literary texts in English and Uzbek and their translations were selected as research material, and based on them, the rendering of linguistic units in translation and their cultural and pragmatic transformations were analyzed in a comprehensive manner.

Results of the Analysis: The analysis identified several main strategies for ensuring pragmatic adequacy in literary translation. These strategies aim to convey the communicative purpose, pragmatic effect, and aesthetic features of the source text into the target language as fully as possible. The pragmatic adaptation strategy involves adjusting the translation to the cultural and linguistic characteristics of the target audience. This approach enhances communicative effectiveness by presenting cultural references in an understandable and acceptable form, thereby facilitating text reception and interpretation.

The compensation strategy is based on restoring pragmatic effects present in the source text through other linguistic means in the target text. This method allows the preservation of emotional and aesthetic impact, and is particularly effective when stylistic nuances are important. The explicitation (explanatory) strategy involves translating complex or unfamiliar units by providing additional explanations. This approach helps the reader correctly and fully understand the content of the text and prevents communicative gaps.

The transformation strategy requires altering the form and content of the text while taking into account structural and semantic differences between language systems. This method includes adjustments at grammatical, lexical, and syntactic levels and is important for ensuring pragmatic adequacy. The cultural substitution strategy involves replacing a cultural element in the source text with an equivalent element in the target culture. This improves text comprehensibility and facilitates the reader's connection with the cultural context.

The stylistic adaptation strategy aims to preserve the author's individual style and artistic expressive means in translation as much as possible. This approach enhances the aesthetic and pragmatic impact of the text and helps maintain its literary value. Overall, the results show that pragmatic adequacy is one of the key factors determining the communicative effectiveness of translation. The coordinated application of these strategies enables the successful transfer of the source text's content, style, and impact into the target language.

Conclusion: Based on the results of the study, the following conclusions were drawn. Ensuring pragmatic adequacy in literary translation is one of the key factors determining the adequacy of translation and the correct reception of the text by the reader. Without pragmatic adequacy, translation may fail to fully convey the communicative purpose of the source text. To achieve pragmatic adequacy, it is necessary to apply strategies such as adaptation, compensation, explicitation, and transformation in a coordinated manner. These strategies help overcome linguistic and cultural differences arising in the translation process and ensure the pragmatic and aesthetic integrity of the text.

The translator's linguoculturological and pragmatic competence directly affects translation quality. These competencies determine the translator's ability to understand cultural context, perceive implicit meanings, and adequately express them in the target language. In literary translation, accurately conveying cultural references is crucial for ensuring pragmatic adequacy. Misinterpretation or insufficient representation of cultural elements may reduce the communicative effectiveness of the text. Therefore, in-depth study of the pragmatic approach

and its effective application in practical translation is recognized as one of the most relevant and перспективные directions in modern translation studies.

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